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Two New Compounds from the Stem bark of *Samanea saman*

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Abstract

From the stem bark of *Samanea saman* two new compounds have been isolated and characterized as stigma -7, 22-diene-3- O [α -L- arabinopyranaosyl (1 \rightarrow 2)] - β -D - galactopyranoside 1 and 19 - hydroxy - octacos - 5 - ene -3 one 2 by spectral and chemical studies.

Key Words: *Samanea saman*, Mimosaceae, Raintree.

Introduction

Samanea saman (Mimosaceae) commonly called "Raintree" is a useful medicinal plant is native of Yucatan Peninsula Guatemala to Peru ,Bolivia, Brazil, throughout the West Indies, in old world tropics and also in Southern Florida¹ but is planted almost throughout India.

The root decoction is used in hot baths for stomach cancer in Venezuela.² Rain tree is a folk remedy for cold, diarrhea, headache, intestine ailments and stomachache.³ The alcoholic extract of the leaves inhibits Mycobacterium tuberculosis.⁴ The alkaloid fraction of the leaves is effective on the CNS and PNS. In Colombia, the fruit decoction is used as a CNS-sedative. The leaf infusion is used as a laxative⁵. In the West Indies, seeds are chewed for sore throat⁶.

Earlier alkaloids,⁷ flavonoids, kaempferol⁸

have been isolated. Ethanolic extract of the stem bark furnished compound 1 and 2 from benzene : ethyl acetate (9:1, v/v). Homogeneity and purity were established by TLC and Co-Pc.

Extraction and Isolation:

The air-dried and finely crushed stem bark (5 kg) of *Samanea saman* was repeatedly extracted with boiling EtOH, concentrated under reduce pressure in a rotatory evaporator and poured into an excess of cold-water to give water soluble and water insoluble portion. The water insoluble portion was extracted successively with different solvents of increasing polarity over a column. Elution with solvent system C₆H₆ : EA (9:1v/v) gave two compound 1 (0.4g) and 2 (0.6g) separate by preparative TLC.

Experimental Section:

The stem bark of *Samanea saman* was collected in April 1999 from the Botany Department, University of Allahabad, Allahabad, U.P., India. Melting points are uncorrected, column, thin layer chromatography analysis were performed at room temperature. Sugars were characterized by descending paper chromatography on Whatmann No. 1 paper, using n-BuOH : AcOH : H₂O (4:1:5) as a developing solvent.

Phytochemical investigation and results

Compound 1: C₄₀H₆₆O₁₀, m.p. 126°C, non-reducing glycoside of steroid showed absorption in the IR spectra for secondary hydroxyl group

(3460 cm⁻¹) trisubstituted double bond (1649 & 792 cm⁻¹) and gem-dimethyl group (1385 and 1375 cm⁻¹). On acid hydrolysis it gave an aglycone 1a and two sugar moieties. Both sugars were identified as D-galactose and L-arabinose on the basis of co-paper chromatography with their authentic samples.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of 1a showed signals for (i) two tertiary methyl group at 0.79 (3H, s) and 0.55 (3H, s) (ii) three secondary methyl group at 1.03 (3H, d, J=6.72 Hz), 0.83 (3H, d, J=6.5 Hz) and 0.85 (3H, d, J=6.92 Hz) (iii) Two olefinic protons at 5.12 (1H, dd, J=15.39 and 9 Hz) and 5.24 (1H, dd, J=15.0 and 8.09 Hz) due to double bond at C-22 (23) (iv) one olefinic proton at C-7 resonated at 5.18 (1H, brs) (v) hydroxy group at C-3 resonated at 5.40 (1H, br) and 3.83 (1H, dd, J=9.6 Hz) showed it equatorial (α) orientation. All the above data indicated the presence of a tetracyclic steroid nucleus with 3-hydroxy group, double bond at C-7 (8), methyl group at C-18 and C-19 and a side chain having double bond and gem-dimethyl group.

In mass spectrum, intense peak at m/z 272 and 140 also confirms the presence of double bond at C-22 (23). which was also supported by ¹³C NMR spectrum, showed two doublet at 131.8 (C-22) and 135.46 (C-23). see ¹³C NMR table. Peaks also observed at 254, 272, 232, 85, 43 & 29. Hence 1a must be stigma 7,22 - diene -3-ol.

Hydrolysis of the glycoside with enzyme takadiastase liberated free arabinose and no galactose in the hydrolysate indicating the β nature of arabinose linkage. After complete takadiastase hydrolysis, the glycoside was hydrolysed with emulsin, galactose was observed in the hydrolysate, confirmed the linkage to be α in nature with the aglycone. The β and α nature of arabinose and galactose was further supported by its ¹H NMR in which the shifts of anomeric protons were appeared at 4.38 (1H, d, J = 7 Hz) and 5.30 (1H, d, J = 8 Hz), respectively. ¹H NMR spectrum showed signals at 3.52 - 3.88 (11H) for sugar protons.

This confirmed that galactose was involved in the glycosidic linkage with the aglycone and arabinose involved in inter glycosidic linkage with C-2' of galactose. Easy hydrolysis eliminated the possibility of C-C glycosidic linkage, so the linkage must be of C-O-C type i.e. at C-3.

On the basis of described facts the structure of the compound 1 was identified as stigma 7, 22-diene-3-O-[- β -L-arabinopyranosyl (1 2)]- α -D-galactopyranoside.

The white coloured compound 2, m.p. 76°C, molecular formula: C₂₈H₅₄O₂ was analysed as 19-hydroxy-octacos-5-ene-3-one on the basis of colour reaction and spectral data.

IR spectrum showed absorption bands at 3420 (hydroxyl group), 1720 (carbonyl group), 1632 and 970 (trans double bond) and presence of bands at 2930, 2850 and 720 cm⁻¹ and absence of absorption in the aromatic region suggested

that it is a long chain aliphatic compound. It decolourized KMnO_4 and Br_2 solution confirming the presence of unsaturation in the compound. It formed hydrazone with 2,4-DNP confirming the presence of carbonyl group.

The ^1H NMR spectrum exhibited absorption peak at 5.20 (2H, t, $J=15$ Hz) for methine proton ($\text{CH}=\text{Ch}$), and at 2.40 (2H, d, $-\text{CO}-\text{CH}_2$) for two methylene protons at C-4 position. Appearance of a triplet 0.94 (6H, t, $2 \times \text{CH}_3$) showed the presence of two methyl group. A broad singlet at 1.40 (36H, brs, $18 \times \text{CH}_2$) indicated the presence of eighteen methylene groups. Signal at 2.26 (2H, q, CH_2CO) showed the presence of one methylene group at C-2 position. The 'J' value of the vinylic protons strongly suggested the trans configuration of the double bond. A four proton multiplet appearing at 2.04 (4H, m, $-\text{H}_2\text{CCH}(\text{OH})\text{CH}_2-$) was attributed to the two methylene units attached to the carbinolic carbon. Multiplet at 3.60 (1H, bm, $-\text{CHOH}$, unresolved) was due to the proton of a methine group bearing the hydroxy group. Hydroxy proton resonated as a singlet at 1.67 ppm.

All the above observation indicated the compound to be an unsaturated aliphatic hydroxy ketone having 28 carbon atoms.

The mass spectrum of the compound exhibited a molecular ion peak, at m/z 422. It is commonly observed that major fragmentation peaks arising from aliphatic ketones results by the cleavage at $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ group with charge retention at the oxygenated fragment as shown:

absence of $[\text{M}+15]$ ion and the presence of $[\text{M}+1]^+$ ion peak suggested the unsymmetrical nature of the compound¹¹. The location of $>\text{C}=\text{O}$ was found to be at C3, from prominent fission ions at m/z 393, 365, 57, 29 and fission ions at 351 and 71. The mass spectral peaks at m/z 295, 265, 157 and 127 showed the presence of hydroxy group at C-19. Thus, the compound 2 was characterized as 19-hydroxy-octacos-5-ene-3-one.

Mass fragmentation of the Compound 1

Compound 2

C NMR(7) values of glycoside Comp -1 and its Aglycone.

Position Assigned	Glycoside Chemical Shift (ppm)	Aglycone Chemical Shift (ppm)
C-1	35.60 (t)	35.60 (t)
C-2	36.20 (t)	36.20 (t)
C-3	58.23 (d)	49.81 (d)
C-4	34.88 (t)	34.90 (t)
C-5	30.85 (d)	30.83 (d)
C-6	28.30 (t)	28.30 (t)
C-7	136.00 (d)	136.00 (d)
C-8	125.26 (s)	125.25 (s)
C-9	31.82 (d)	31.82 (d)
C-10	52.00 (s)	52.00 (s)
C-11	21.96 (t)	21.96 (t)
C-12	39.59 (t)	39.59 (t)
C-13	42.24 (s)	42.24 (s)
C-14	55.00 (d)	55.00 (d)
C-15	24.16 (t)	24.15 (t)
C-16	28.82 (d)	28.82 (t)
C-17	55.97 (d)	55.95 (d)
C-18	13.40 (q)	13.40 (q)
C-19	17.85 (q)	17.85 (q)
C-20	40.45 (d)	40.45 (d)
C-21	22.65 (q)	22.65 (q)
C-22	131.80 (d)	131.80 (d)
C-23	135.46 (d)	135.46 (d)
C-24	52.29 (d)	52.29 (d)
C-25	31.85 (d)	31.85 (d)
C-26	21.13 (q)	21.12 (q)
C-27	20.00 (q)	20.00 (q)
C-28	26.35 (t)	26.35 (t)
C-29	14.30 (q)	14.30 (q)
C-1'	98.20 (d)	
C-2'	79.80 (d)	
C-3'	71.90 (d)	
C-4'	67.30 (d)	
C-5'	74.60 (d)	
C-6'	60.80 (t)	
C-1''	103.80 (d)	
C-2''	71.60 (d)	
C-3''	75.20 (d)	
C-4''	70.30 (d)	
C-5''	67.20 (t)	

Conclusion

The structures of these compounds have been elucidated by IR, MS and NMR spectral analysis. However to our knowledge from the survey of literature stigma7, 22-diene-3-O-[- - Larabinopyranosyl (1 \rightarrow 2)]- -D-galactopyranoside and 19-hydroxy-octacos-5-ene-3-one were previously unknown from *Samanea saman*.

References:

1. James Duke A., Handbook of Energy Crop. 1983.
2. Hartwell J.L., Plants used against cancer, A Surey Lloydia, 30-34, 1967-1971.
3. Duke J.A. and Wain K.K., Medicinal plants of the World, 3, 1981.
4. Pery LM., Medicinal plants of east and Southeast Asia, MIT press, Cambridge, 1980.
5. Garcia-Barriga H., Flora medicinal de Colombia. Botanica Medica. Talleres Editoriales de la Imprenta Nacional. Bogota, 1975.
6. Ayensu E.S, Medicinal plants of the West Indies, Reference Publications, Inc. Algonac, MI, 282, 1981.
7. CSIR, The Wealth of India, New Delhi, 11, 1948-1976.
8. List P.H. and Horhammer L., Hager's Handbuchder pharmazeutischen praxis, Springer I - Verlag, Berlin, 2-6, 1969-1979.
9. Nakamura T.; Katsumi R.; Sazawa T.; Mizumo T. and Hagiwara T., Phytochemistry, 27, 1988, 2777.
10. Sati O.P; Bahuguna S.; Uniyal S. and Bhakuni D.S., 28(2), 1989, 575.
11. Stoianoya -Ivanova B. and Hadjieva P., Phytochemistry, 8, 1969, 1549